

RESEARCH ARTICLE

AI-based services for inclusive language learning in immersive XR environments: Speech translation, and sign language integration

[version 1; peer review: 1 not approved]

Nikolaos D. Tantaroudas¹, Andrew J. McCracken², Ilias Karachalios³, Evangelos Papatheou⁴

¹Institute of Communications and Computer Systems (ICCS), Iroon Polytechniou 9,Zografou, Athens, 15773, Greece

²DASKALOS-APPS, PERONNAS, 01960, France

³National Technical University of Athens, Zografou, Attica, Greece

⁴Small-Scale Robotics Laboratory, University of Exeter Engineering, Exeter, England, EX4 4QF, UK

V1 First published: 11 Mar 2026, 6:72
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.23214.1>
Latest published: 13 Jun 2026, 6:72
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.23214.2>

Abstract

Background

Extended Reality (XR) technologies offer transformative potential for language education, yet current platforms largely neglect the accessibility needs of deaf and hard-of-hearing individuals. Existing solutions typically operate in single-language environments and lack integrated support for sign language and multimodal communication. There is a critical need for inclusive platforms that serve both deaf and hearing learners through cross-modal AI services embedded in immersive environments.

Methods

This study presents a modular platform integrating six AI services: speech-to-text transcription (OpenAI Whisper), multilingual translation (Meta NLLB), text-to-speech synthesis (AWS Polly), sentiment analysis (RoBERTa), session summarisation (flan-t5-base-samsum), and International Sign (IS) translation via Google MediaPipe. An IS dataset of 750 gesture videos was processed to extract hand landmark coordinates mapped to 3D avatar animations within a Unity-based VR environment on Meta Quest 3 headsets. The system was validated through technical benchmarking of AI service performance, including comparative evaluation of text-to-speech services and multilingual

Open Peer Review

Approval Status

1

version 2

(revision)

13 Jun 2026

version 1

11 Mar 2026

[view](#)

1. **Diego Resende Faria**, Loughborough

University Department of Computer Science
(Ringgold ID: 152591), Loughborough, UK

Any reports and responses or comments on the article can be found at the end of the article.

translation models (NLLB-200 and EuroLLM 1.7B variants), as well as load testing to assess platform scalability.

Results

Technical benchmarking confirmed the platform's viability for real-time XR deployment. TTS benchmarking confirmed AWS Polly's lowest latency (50–100 ms first byte) at competitive cost. The EuroLLM 1.7B Instruct model achieved a BLEU score of 84.34, outperforming NLLB's 79.25. Load testing with 1,000 simulated concurrent users demonstrated average response times under 800 milliseconds with no critical failures. Avatar animation latency for IS sign rendering remained consistently under 300 milliseconds.

Conclusions

The results demonstrate the feasibility of integrating cross-modal AI services within XR environments for accessible, multilingual language learning. The modular architecture enables independent scaling and adaptation to diverse contexts, laying the groundwork for equitable educational solutions aligned with EU digital accessibility objectives.

Plain Language summary

Learning a new language can be challenging, and it is even more difficult for deaf individuals who rely on sign language. This study addresses the challenge by creating a virtual reality (VR) learning environment where a digital 3D character (avatar) can speak, translate, and perform sign language in real time. The system uses several artificial intelligence tools working together: one that converts speech into text, another that translates text between multiple languages, a third that converts text back into spoken language, and a fourth that translates text into International Sign Language gestures performed by the avatar. Users wear a VR headset and interact with the avatar in a virtual classroom where they can select their preferred language and receive immediate translations in both spoken and signed forms. The system's technical performance was validated through benchmarking of AI translation models, text-to-speech services, and scalability testing, confirming its suitability for real-time educational applications. This research is a step toward creating virtual learning environments where language barriers and hearing limitations no longer prevent people from accessing education.

Keywords

Extended Reality, Artificial Intelligence, International Sign Language, Language Learning, Accessibility, 3D Avatars, Multilingual Translation, Speech Recognition

This article is included in the [Horizon Europe gateway](#).

This article is included in the [Artificial Intelligence and the Social Sciences and Humanities collection](#).

Corresponding author: Nikolaos D. Tantaroudas (nikolaos.tantaroudas@iccs.gr)

Author roles: **Tantaroudas ND:** Conceptualization, Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Funding Acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Supervision, Validation, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **J. McCracken A:** Conceptualization, Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Funding Acquisition, Methodology, Project Administration, Software, Writing – Review & Editing; **Karachalios I:** Investigation, Methodology, Resources, Validation, Visualization, Writing – Review & Editing; **Papatheou E:** Conceptualization, Data Curation, Investigation, Methodology, Resources, Supervision, Validation, Writing – Review & Editing

Competing interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Grant information: This research was supported by FSTP Funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101070631 (UTTER — Unified Transcription and Translation for Extended Reality) and from the UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee (Grant No. 10039436). Views and opinions expressed are those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor the granting authority. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. The funding body had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

Copyright: © 2026 Tantaroudas ND *et al.* This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

How to cite this article: Tantaroudas ND, J. McCracken A, Karachalios I and Papatheou E. **AI-based services for inclusive language learning in immersive XR environments: Speech translation, and sign language integration [version 1; peer review: 1 not approved]** Open Research Europe 2026, 6:72 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.23214.1>

First published: 11 Mar 2026, 6:72 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.23214.1>

Introduction

Foreign language acquisition has historically relied on structured pedagogical approaches, including grammar-translation methods, audio-lingual drills, and immersion techniques.^{1,2} The grammar-translation approach, rooted in classical education, emphasises textual analysis and memorisation of grammatical rules, while audio-lingual methods focus on pattern repetition and habitual formation.¹ Immersion-based strategies aim to replicate natural language acquisition by embedding learners in target-language contexts.² Over the past few decades, technological tools such as language laboratories, multimedia programmes, and computer-assisted instruction have augmented these traditional approaches, allowing learners to practice independently.^{2,3}

The emergence of Extended Reality (XR), encompassing Augmented Reality (AR), Virtual Reality (VR), and Mixed Reality (MR), has introduced transformative possibilities for language education by providing immersive, context-rich simulations that transcend the limitations of traditional classroom settings.^{3,4} AR overlays digital content onto the physical world, enhancing vocabulary acquisition through contextualised visual and auditory stimuli, while VR fully immerses users in synthetic environments where they can engage in conversational practice with virtual interlocutors.^{4,5} Recent studies have demonstrated that VR environments can improve learners' speaking confidence and reduce anxiety by offering risk-free, repeatable practice opportunities.^{6,7} Commercial platforms such as ImmerseMe VR⁸ enable learners to navigate realistic scenarios, such as ordering food in a restaurant or asking for directions, thereby promoting contextual learning, while AR applications like MondlyAR⁹ leverage spatial anchoring to reinforce vocabulary retention.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) complements XR by powering adaptive learning systems, natural language processing (NLP), and real-time feedback mechanisms.¹⁰ AI-driven 3D avatars within XR environments can deliver personalised language instruction, facilitate conversational practice, and adapt to individual learner needs, creating a more engaging and effective educational experience.^{5,11} The integration of AI with XR has been identified as a key enabler of immersive, learner-centred approaches to language acquisition, closing the gap between controlled classroom exercises and authentic communicative practice.^{6,12}

However, significant gaps remain in the accessibility and inclusivity of current XR-based language learning solutions.^{13,12} Most existing platforms are designed for single-language environments or narrowly defined use cases, limiting their utility for multilingual and multicultural learners.¹³ More critically, these systems largely neglect the needs of deaf and hard-of-hearing individuals, who require sign language support to participate effectively in language education.^{14,15} Although advances in AI-driven sign language recognition have been achieved, the development of comprehensive text-to-sign translation systems remains constrained by insufficient annotated datasets, low accuracy in gesture recognition, and the absence of real-time translation capabilities within XR environments.^{16,17} Current challenges are compounded by the diversity of sign languages across regions, with most research focusing on American Sign Language (ASL) while largely overlooking International Sign (IS), a visual communication system used by deaf individuals from diverse linguistic backgrounds in international contexts.^{18,19}

Furthermore, while AI-driven avatars hold great promise for natural, culturally sensitive language instruction, they currently struggle to deliver accurate interactions across different languages and cultural nuances due to challenges in NLP algorithms and the complexity of implementing diverse linguistic databases.^{14,20} Robust pedagogical frameworks that guide the effective integration of XR technologies into language curricula are also needed to ensure that technological innovation translates into meaningful educational outcomes.^{12,21}

The need for inclusive educational technologies is further underscored by European Union policy frameworks, including the European Accessibility Act and the European Strategy for the Rights of Persons with Disabilities 2021–2030, which call for accessible digital services and equitable participation in education across member states. The EU's Digital Education Action Plan (2021–2027) specifically highlights the role of emerging technologies, including AI and immersive environments, in encouraging inclusive and high-quality education. Despite these policy initiatives, there remains a significant gap between the accessibility aspirations articulated in EU frameworks and the practical capabilities of current XR-based educational platforms, particularly regarding support for sign language users and multilingual learners.

This paper addresses these gaps by presenting a comprehensive platform that integrates modular AI-driven services for inclusive language learning in immersive XR environments. Building upon and extending our earlier conference publication,^{22,47,48} this paper provides an expanded literature review, describes the complete system architecture, presents quantitative benchmarking analyses of AI translation models and text-to-speech services, and discusses the implications for equitable educational technology. The contributions of this work can be summarised as follows: (a) the design and implementation of a modular, interoperable framework that combines speech-to-text, text-to-speech,

text-to-text translation, sentiment analysis, and IS translation within a unified XR platform; (b) the creation of an IS gesture dataset comprising 750 videos processed using Google MediaPipe for real-time avatar-driven sign language delivery; (c) quantitative benchmarking of multilingual translation models (NLLB-200 vs. EuroLLM) and text-to-speech services; and (d) a scalability evaluation demonstrating robust performance under simulated high-demand scenarios.

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows. Section 2 presents the related work across XR for education, AI-driven translation, sign language processing, and session summarisation. Section 3 details the methodology and system architecture. Section 4 presents the results, including AI service implementations, and benchmarking analyses. Section 5 discusses the findings and their implications, and Section 6 concludes the paper with directions for future work.

Related work

Extended reality for language education

The application of XR technologies in education has grown substantially, driven by the recognition that immersive environments can enhance engagement, motivation, and learning retention.^{3,4} In the context of language learning, VR provides a unique opportunity to situate learners within authentic communicative contexts, enabling them to practice speaking, listening, and interacting in a target language without the social pressures of real-world interactions.^{6,7} Divekar et al.³ demonstrated that foreign language acquisition systems combining AI with XR can significantly improve learner outcomes by providing contextualised, adaptive interactions. Tegoan et al.⁴ conducted a systematic review of XR applications for language teaching, concluding that immersive technologies offer distinct advantages in promoting experiential learning, though they also identified limitations related to content design and pedagogical alignment.

Research by Zhi and Wu⁷ proposed a cognitive-affective model of immersive learning, arguing that XR-based language learning environments enhance both cognitive processing and emotional engagement, leading to deeper learning outcomes. Godwin-Jones⁶ explored the concepts of presence and agency in virtual spaces, highlighting the promise of XR for creating authentic language learning experiences where learners can exercise autonomy and make meaningful communicative choices. Panagiotidis⁵ examined VR applications specifically designed for language learning, finding that virtual environments can effectively supplement traditional instruction by offering novel modalities for practice and assessment.

Despite these advances, Taborda et al.¹³ noted that engagement and attention in XR learning environments remain under-researched, with limited understanding of how immersive features affect sustained learning. Zhang et al.¹² identified a need for stronger theoretical frameworks to guide the integration of mixed reality technologies into language curricula, arguing that without such frameworks, the deployment of XR tools risks being technologically driven rather than pedagogically grounded. Garcia et al.¹⁰ explored the intersection of AI and XR in design education, identifying both challenges and opportunities that arise when emerging technologies are applied in educational contexts.

AI-driven speech recognition and translation in XR

Advances in automatic speech recognition (ASR) have been accelerated by deep learning architectures, particularly encoder-decoder frameworks and transformer models.^{23,24} OpenAI's Whisper model represents a significant milestone in ASR, achieving robust multilingual speech recognition through training on over 680,000 hours of weakly supervised audio data.²³ Whisper's ability to generalise across languages and acoustic conditions makes it well-suited for integration into XR environments where real-time, accurate transcription is essential for inclusive communication.^{11,23}

Multilingual translation has also seen substantial progress through models such as Meta's No Language Left Behind (NLLB), which supports translation across 200 languages using a conditional compute architecture based on Sparsely Gated Mixture of Experts.²⁴ The NLLB model achieves a 44% improvement in BLEU scores relative to previous state-of-the-art systems, with particular gains for low-resource languages.²⁴ In XR contexts, real-time translation services facilitate collaboration among multilingual users, effectively overcoming language barriers and enriching user interactions.^{20,21} Research has focused on bridging the modality gap between speech and text to ensure effective cross-modal communication within immersive environments,²⁵ while multilingual audio-visual corpora such as MuAViC have been developed to support robust speech-to-text translation across modalities.²⁶

Hartholt et al.¹¹ described a multi-platform framework for embodied AI agents in XR, demonstrating the potential of virtual humans to serve as ubiquitous interaction partners that can deliver contextualised language instruction. Sylaiou et al.²⁰ explored the use of XR technologies for fostering visitor experience and inclusion at industrial museums, demonstrating how real-time transcription and translation can enhance accessibility in cultural settings. Hirzle et al.²¹ provided a scoping review of the intersection between XR and AI, mapping the landscape of research at this convergence and identifying key opportunities and challenges for future development.

Sign language translation and recognition

AI has significantly advanced sign language translation and recognition, facilitating communication between deaf and hearing individuals by converting spoken or written language into sign language gestures.^{17,27} Deep learning models, particularly transformer-based architectures, have led to substantial improvements in both translation accuracy and efficiency.^{16,28} Current systems often utilise gloss annotation, which decomposes signs into linguistic components to enhance translation quality,²⁷ while newer gloss-free approaches have demonstrated comparable results by eliminating this intermediate step.²⁸ Visual-language pretraining techniques have proven effective in enhancing both the accuracy and scalability of sign language translation, as demonstrated on benchmark datasets such as PHOENIX14T and CSL-Daily.^{27,29} Contrastive visual-textual transformation approaches, such as CVT-SLR, have been proposed for sign language recognition with variational alignment, achieving strong results on standard benchmarks.²⁹ Additionally, modern wearable and sensor-based technologies have the potential to complement AI systems by enabling real-time gesture recognition and enhancing accessibility for individuals with hearing impairments.³⁰ Taborri et al.¹⁴ reviewed the use of AI for sign language recognition in education, with a focus on the ISENSE project, while Strobel et al.¹⁵ applied design science research to develop AI-based sign language translation systems. Google MediaPipe has emerged as a powerful open-source framework for real-time hand and body tracking, providing 21 three-dimensional hand landmarks from single video frames.³¹ Its lightweight architecture and ability to run on mobile devices make it particularly suitable for integration with XR applications where computational efficiency is critical. MediaPipe has been widely adopted in sign language recognition research, enabling the extraction of precise hand and finger coordinates that serve as input features for gesture classification models.^{31,32} Despite these advances, significant challenges remain, particularly in developing comprehensive systems for International Sign (IS). Unlike national sign languages such as ASL or British Sign Language, IS is a visual communication system used by deaf individuals from diverse linguistic backgrounds in international contexts, such as conferences, sporting events, and educational settings.^{18,33} Online sign language repositories such as SpreadTheSign⁴⁵ have contributed to cross-linguistic accessibility by providing video demonstrations of signs across multiple national sign languages, serving as valuable training resources for computational models. Recent work by Srivastava et al.⁴⁶ demonstrated the effectiveness of MediaPipe Holistic combined with deep learning architectures for continuous sign language recognition, achieving promising results that underscore the potential of landmark-based approaches for real-time gesture classification. However, while some progress has been made with ASL translation models,³⁴ advanced implementations for IS remain scarce, and the animation of sign language gestures via avatars in XR environments represents an open research challenge.^{19,22}

Large language models for session summarisation

Large Language Models (LLMs) have advanced the capabilities of automatic summarisation by generating coherent and contextually appropriate summaries of complex data.^{35,36} Models such as GPT-4 and fine-tuned variants of T5 and BART excel at processing large datasets and extracting relevant information, making them well-suited for session summarisation in educational contexts.³⁶ In XR environments, LLMs can synthesise immersive experiences by summarising key interactions, enabling learners to revisit essential insights from their sessions. The ability of LLMs to perform abstractive summarisation allows them to generate coherent narratives rather than mere repetitions of content, enhancing learning retention.³⁶ Bozkir et al.³⁷ explored the embedding of LLMs into XR, identifying opportunities and challenges for inclusion, engagement, and privacy. Boros and Oyamada³⁶ investigated LLM organisation for abstractive summarisation, while Ramprasad et al.³⁸ analysed LLM behaviour in dialogue summarisation, unveiling trends in circumstantial hallucinations that can affect factual accuracy. Addressing hallucination through fine-tuning and task-specific training remains an important area for solidifying the role of LLMs in adaptive learning systems within XR.³⁸

Sentiment analysis in educational technology

Sentiment analysis has gained traction as a means of enriching communication in educational technology by detecting and conveying emotional cues. Transformer-based models such as RoBERTa have demonstrated strong performance in classifying textual inputs into emotional categories.³⁹ In the context of XR-based language learning, sentiment analysis can enrich avatar-mediated communication by mapping detected emotions to visual cues, such as emoticons, thereby providing additional contextual information that enhances emotional clarity and social presence for learners.^{22,39}

Methodology

Conceptual framework and system architecture

The proposed platform integrates modular AI-driven services designed for both deaf and hearing individuals within immersive XR environments. The system architecture, illustrated in [Figure 1](#), follows a service-oriented approach where each AI capability, speech-to-text, text-to-speech, text-to-text translation, text-to-sign translation, sentiment analysis, and session summarisation, is deployed as an independent microservice accessible via RESTful APIs. This modular design ensures flexibility, scalability, and interoperability across XR platforms.

Figure 1. High-level description of the proposed system architecture.

The services are hosted on AWS Cloud infrastructure, ensuring high availability and the ability to scale horizontally to accommodate increasing user loads. In VR settings, 3D avatars function as virtual tutors, delivering real-time language learning through text and speech translation for hearing users and text-to-sign translation for deaf users. The XR scenarios were designed in consultation with educators and language acquisition experts to ensure pedagogical relevance, aligning AI services with established communicative and task-based learning approaches.

To ensure scalability, the platform employs Docker-based orchestration and cloud-native compatibility, enabling horizontal scaling of individual AI microservices. A load testing campaign simulated 1,000 concurrent users sending simultaneous API requests to the backend services, with the system maintaining an average response time under 800 milliseconds and recording no critical failures, confirming robust performance under high-demand educational scenarios.

Speech-to-text transcription

The speech-to-text component leverages OpenAI's Whisper model,²³ an open-source ASR system trained on over 680,000 hours of multilingual and multitask supervised data. Whisper employs a sequence-to-sequence transformer architecture that processes audio spectrograms and generates transcriptions, supporting robust performance across diverse languages and acoustic conditions. The platform deploys Whisper as an API service that receives audio input from users within the VR environment and returns real-time text transcriptions. Figure 2 illustrates the speech-to-text transcription process in Greek, demonstrating accurate conversion of spoken inputs into text. The terminal output shows

```

(venv) andrew-daskalos@Mac ASR % python -u test.py
Reading metadata...: 1696it [00:00, 7038.75it/s]
The attention mask is not set and cannot be inferred from input because pad token is same as eos token. As a consequence, you may observe unexpected behavior. Please pass your input's 'attention_mask' to obtain reliable results.
ASR test on file el_test_0/common_voice_el_27443549.mp3. Expected: Γιατί την αλυσίδα μου την είχε δώσει εμένα
Actual: ['γιατί την αλυσίδα μου την είχε δώσει εμένα']
  
```

Figure 2. Speech-to-text transcription using a Whisper AI wrapper.²³

real-time transcription of Greek speech input, demonstrating accurate processing of spoken language into text for subsequent translation and display within the XR environment.

Multilingual text-to-text translation

For multilingual translation, the platform integrates Meta’s No Language Left Behind (NLLB) model,²⁴ a conditional compute model based on Sparsely Gated Mixture of Experts that supports translation across 200 languages. The NLLB-200-distilled-600 M variant is deployed as a translation API service, enabling real-time conversion of transcribed text between multiple language pairs. The translation service is chained sequentially with the speech-to-text service, creating an automated pipeline where user speech is first transcribed into text and then translated into the target language selected by the user. Figure 3 demonstrates the text-to-text translation workflow using NLLB, showcasing real-time translation across multiple languages. The system translates text in real time across multiple languages, enabling multilingual interactions within the XR learning environment.

Text-to-speech synthesis

The text-to-speech (TTS) component generates natural, real-time audio output in the target language. Initially, the platform explored the Coqui TTS Tacotron2-DDC model⁴⁰ and the open-source Piper TTS system.⁴¹ However, due to security vulnerabilities associated with poorly maintained Python dependencies in Piper and limitations in voice naturalness with Tacotron2-DDC, the team transitioned to AWS Polly, a production-grade TTS service that offers low-latency, high-quality speech synthesis across 34 languages.

The selection of AWS Polly was informed by a comprehensive benchmarking study comparing four TTS services: AWS Polly Standard, Google Cloud TTS Standard, Microsoft Azure Speech, and ElevenLabs. Table 1 presents the latency performance metrics, which were derived from both the Picovoice TTS Latency Benchmark study⁴² and our own testing. Table 1 provides the latency performance metrics for text-to-speech services. AWS Polly was selected for its consistently low first-byte latency (50–100 ms), cost-effectiveness (\$4 per million characters), and sufficient language and voice variety for the target application. The TTS service is integrated with the translation pipeline, providing multilingual spoken feedback through the 3D avatar system.

Figure 3. Text-to-text translation workflow using Meta’s NLLB model.²⁴

Table 1. Latency performance metrics for text-to-speech services.

Service	First byte latency	FTTS	Total response time
AWS Polly Standard	50-100 ms	450 ms	780 ms
Google Cloud Standard	300-2000 ms	600 ms	1200 ms
Microsoft Azure	150-800 ms	1140 ms	1500 ms
ElevenLabs	300-500 ms	840 ms	1250 ms

Sentiment analysis with emoticon mapping

To enrich avatar-mediated communication with emotional context, the platform incorporates a sentiment analysis module based on the twitter-roberta-base-sentiment model from CardiffNLP.³⁹ This RoBERTa-based transformer processes translated text input and classifies it into sentiment categories such as “happy,” “neutral,” or “sad.” Each detected sentiment is mapped to a corresponding emoticon that is displayed in real time within the VR scene adjacent to the avatar, enhancing affective expressiveness and social presence. Figure 4 demonstrates the emoticon-based sentiment feedback displayed in the XR environment. The RoBERTa-based sentiment classifier processes the avatar’s speech output and maps detected emotions to visual emoticons displayed alongside the avatar, providing additional contextual and emotional cues for learners. Figure 5 shows the API request and response format for the sentiment analysis module, illustrating the RESTful interface through which the VR application communicates with the sentiment service. The interface accepts JSON-formatted text input and returns classified sentiment labels with associated confidence scores for multiple emotional categories.

Meeting summarisation module

The platform integrates the flan-t5-base-samsum model,⁴³ available on Hugging Face, for real-time summarisation of dialogues in multilingual XR-based educational scenarios. This model is deployed as an API on AWS Lambda as part of the platform’s backend services. It is designed for deaf or hard-of-hearing users, interpreters, and educators to receive concise, natural language summaries of verbal exchanges within the XR scene. Figure 6 presents the API interface for the summarisation module, showing how input dialogue is processed and condensed into a coherent summary. The system processes dialogue text and generates concise summaries, with the response including both the original text and the summarised output along with token count statistics.

International Sign (IS) translation

A key contribution of this work is the development of an IS translation pipeline. During the research phase, an extensive review revealed that while each country has its own distinct sign language with unique linguistic structures, IS serves as a broadly understood visual communication system used by deaf individuals from diverse linguistic backgrounds in international contexts.^{18,33} Unlike national sign languages, IS draws on signs from multiple sign languages, iconic gestures, and universal visual cues to enable understanding across national boundaries.

To develop the IS translation model, approximately 750 videos of IS gestures were collected and processed using Google MediaPipe³¹ and OpenCV,⁴⁴ extracting key movement coordinates and hand position data from 21 three-dimensional

Figure 4. Emoticon-based sentiment feedback in the XR environment.

Figure 5. API request and response format for the RoBERTA-based sentiment analysis module.

hand landmarks per frame. The MediaPipe Hands solution provides a machine learning pipeline that infers hand landmarks from single frames, outputting 21 key points per hand with x, y, and z coordinates normalised to the image frame. For each gesture video, frames were extracted at a uniform sampling rate and processed through the MediaPipe pipeline to obtain temporal sequences of landmark positions. These sequences were then normalised relative to the wrist landmark to account for variations in hand size, camera distance, and signer morphology. The normalised landmark sequences were aggregated into a structured dataset associating each sequence with its corresponding IS sign label. Resources such as HandSpeak³⁴ and SpreadTheSign⁴⁵ provided reference video demonstrations of IS signs, which were used both for dataset curation and validation of sign-to-label mappings.

This dataset served as the basis for training a gesture classification model that maps text inputs to corresponding IS signs. An API was developed to map the classified hand positions and gestures to 3D avatar animations within the Unity-based VR environment, enabling real-time IS interpretation. The avatar animation system translates the classified landmark sequences into joint rotations applied to the avatar’s skeletal rig, with interpolation between keyframes to ensure smooth transitions. Preliminary evaluations show that avatar animation latency remains consistently under 300 milliseconds,

```

Curl
curl -X 'POST' \
  'http://localhost:8000/interact/summarize-dialogue' \
  -H 'accept: application/json' \
  -H 'content-type: application/json' \
  -d '{
    "text": "Maria: Good morning everyone. I wanted to touch base about our development priorities for next month.\n\nJohn: Morning. I've been looking at the ticket backlog, and we have several critical issues with the authentication module that need to be addressed.\n\nAndrew: Yes, I've noticed those too. The session timeout issue is causing problems for our enterprise clients.\n\nMaria: Let's prioritize that first then, what about the new feature requirements from marketing?\n\nJohn: I think we can push those to the following sprint. The API integration work is more pressing in my opinion.\n\nAndrew: I agree with John. I've already started working on the database schema updates needed for the API integration.\n\nMaria: That makes sense, we should also all allocate some time for technical debt reduction. The test coverage on the payment module is below our standards.\n\nJohn: Good point. I can assign someone from my team to focus on improving those tests.\n\nAndrew: While we're discussing testing, we should revisit our CI pipeline. The build times have increased significantly.\n\nMaria: Let's add that to the sprint backlog. Can you document the specific issues you're seeing with the pipeline, Andrew?\n\nAndrew: Will do. I'll have something ready by tomorrow.\n\nMaria: Perfect. Let's also make sure we have proper documentation for all these changes. The last deployment caused confusion because of outdated docs.\n\nJohn: I'll update our deployment procedures and share them with the team.\n\nMaria: Great. Anything else we should discuss for next month?\n\nAndrew: Just a heads-up that I'll be out for a conference during the second week.\n\nMaria: Thanks for letting us know. We'll plan around that. If there's nothing else, let's reconvene next week to finalize the sprint planning."
  }'

Request URL
http://localhost:8000/interact/summarize-dialogue

Server response
Code  Details
200
Response body
{
  "original_text": "Maria: Good morning everyone. I wanted to touch base about our development priorities for next month.\n\nJohn: Morning. I've been looking at the ticket backlog, and we have several critical issues with the authentication module that need to be addressed.\n\nAndrew: Yes, I've noticed those too. The session timeout issue is causing problems for our enterprise clients.\n\nMaria: Let's prioritize that first then, what about the new feature requirements from marketing?\n\nJohn: I think we can push those to the following sprint. The API integration work is more pressing in my opinion.\n\nAndrew: I agree with John. I've already started working on the database schema updates needed for the API integration.\n\nMaria: That makes sense, we should also all allocate some time for technical debt reduction. The test coverage on the payment module is below our standards.\n\nJohn: Good point. I can assign someone from my team to focus on improving those tests.\n\nAndrew: While we're discussing testing, we should revisit our CI pipeline. The build times have increased significantly.\n\nMaria: Let's add that to the sprint backlog. Can you document the specific issues you're seeing with the pipeline, Andrew?\n\nAndrew: Will do. I'll have something ready by tomorrow.\n\nMaria: Perfect. Let's also make sure we have proper documentation for all these changes. The last deployment caused confusion because of outdated docs.\n\nJohn: I'll update our deployment procedures and share them with the team.\n\nMaria: Great. Anything else we should discuss for next month?\n\nAndrew: Just a heads-up that I'll be out for a conference during the second week.\n\nMaria: Thanks for letting us know. We'll plan around that. If there's nothing else, let's reconvene next week to finalize the sprint planning.",
  "summary": "Maria, John, Andrew and the team discuss their development priorities for next month. They will focus on the new feature requirements from marketing and the API integration work. Andrew will document the specific issues he is seeing with the CI pipeline. Andrew is going to be out of town for the second week of the month.",
  "token_count": 386
}

Response headers
content-length: 2163
content-type: application/json
date: Fri, 02 May 2025 08:15:28 GMT
server: uvicorn
    
```

Figure 6. API request and response format for the meeting summarisation module based on the flan-t5-base-samsun model.⁴³

Figure 7. Visual sequence of real-time avatar animation driven by extracted gesture landmarks from the IS dataset.

ensuring natural, real-time communication for XR users. Figure 7 presents a visual sequence of the real-time avatar animation pipeline, showing how extracted gesture landmarks are translated into avatar movements. The left panels show the original hand gesture videos with overlaid MediaPipe landmarks (in red and blue), while the right panels illustrate the corresponding 3D avatar performing the recognised sign within the VR environment.

Immersive VR learning environment

The final application was built using the Unity game engine and deployed on Meta Quest 3 headsets, providing a fully immersive learning experience. The Unity development environment was chosen for its cross-platform compatibility, extensive asset ecosystem, and native support for XR development through the XR Interaction Toolkit and OpenXR standards. The Meta Quest 3 headset was selected as the target deployment platform due to its standalone operation (requiring no tethered PC), high-resolution passthrough capabilities for potential AR extensions, and growing adoption in educational and enterprise settings.

Figure 8. Immersive VR-based language learning system.

Figure 8 illustrates the immersive VR classroom environment where a 3D avatar stands in a virtual classroom equipped with multilingual AI tools. Users interact with the system by selecting their preferred language through an interactive questionnaire presented within the VR interface; in response, the avatar provides real-time translations in both spoken language and IS-based sign translations of selected words and phrases. The avatar's animation system supports lip-sync with generated speech output and gestural animation for IS signs, with blending between idle, speaking, and signing states managed through Unity's Animator Controller.

This environment demonstrates how speech-to-text, text-to-sign translation, and text-to-speech services converge to create equitable, self-directed learning opportunities for both deaf and hearing users. The AI-powered avatar delivers educational content in a simulated classroom environment, translating spoken language into International Sign (IS) within a multilingual VR setting. The environment is designed for equitable access and cross-linguistic interaction, with all AI services hosted on scalable AWS Cloud infrastructure.

Figure 9 shows a snapshot of the pipeline from voice input to sign and spoken output in the Meta Quest 3 environment. The avatar is shown delivering IS signs in the virtual classroom environment, with text display panels visible for transcription and translation output.

Results

System implementation and integration

The proposed platform successfully integrates six AI-driven services into a cohesive XR learning experience. Table 2 summarises the implemented services, their underlying models, and key performance characteristics.

TTS benchmarking

Beyond the latency analysis presented in Table 1, voice quality metrics were also evaluated. Table 3 presents the Mean Opinion Score (MOS) and Word Error Rate (WER) values reported by service providers for the compared TTS services. Table 4 summarises the service capabilities, which are important considerations for ensuring the platform remains accessible. Based on the benchmarking, AWS Polly Standard was selected for the proposed platform due to its lowest and most consistent first-byte latency (50–100 ms), cost-effectiveness (\$4 per million characters), and consistent performance across testing sessions, avoiding the high variability observed with other services.

Benchmarking NLLB against EuroLLM

To evaluate potential improvements to the translation component, a comprehensive benchmark comparison was conducted between the deployed NLLB-200-distilled-600 M model and two variants of the EuroLLM 1.7B model. All experiments were performed on a consumer-grade workstation equipped with an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 4060 GPU

Figure 9. MVP demonstration showing multilingual avatar interaction in VR.

Table 2. Summary of AI Services implemented in the proposed platform.

Service	Model/Technology	Key characteristic
Speech-to-text	OpenAI Whisper ²³	Multilingual ASR, 680 k + hours training data
Text-to-Text translation	Meta NLLB-200 ²⁴	200 languages, Mixture of Experts architecture
Text-to-Speech	AWS Polly	34 languages, Mixture of Experts architecture
Sentiment	RoBERTa	Multi-class emotion classification
Session Summarisation	flan-t5-base-samsum ⁴³	Abstractive dialogue summarisation
IS Translation	MediPipe and AVATAR animation ³¹	750 gesture videos, <300 ms animation latency

Table 3. Voice quality metrics for text-to-speech services.

Service	Mean Opinion Score (MOS)	Word error rate
AWS Polly Standard	3.5–3.8	4.2
Google Cloud Standard	3.2–3.5	Variable
Microsoft Azure	3.8–4.0	3.0
ElevenLabs	3.83–4.2	2.83

Table 4. Service capabilities of TTS services (standard models).

Service	Languages	Voices	Max length
AWS Polly Standard	34	66	3000
Google Cloud Standard	40+	220+	5000
Microsoft Azure	140+	110+	5000
ElevenLabs	29	5000+	5000

Table 5. NLLB vs EuroLLM performance comparison.

Metric	NLLB-200	EuroLLM 1.7B Base	EuroLLM 1.7B Instruct
Average BLEU Score	79.25	27.58	84.34
Average Translation Time (s)	0,596	1.509	0.529
Model Load Time (s)	26.63	25.37	40.99
Memory Usage (GB)	~2.5	~3.5	~3.5
Successful Translations	10/10	10/10	10/10

(8 GB VRAM), ensuring that the benchmarking conditions reflect realistic deployment scenarios rather than high-end server infrastructure. The benchmarking used a test dataset of 10 English-to-French translations with varying complexity levels: simple conversational phrases (3 examples), medium-complexity technical sentences (4 examples), and complex sentences with specialised terminology (3 examples). Models were loaded sequentially to manage the limited GPU memory, and inference was conducted using float16 precision to maximise throughput within the available VRAM. For each model, translation quality (BLEU scores), inference speed, and resource utilisation were measured. Table 5 presents the comparative results.

The key findings from the benchmarking are as follows. The EuroLLM 1.7B Instruct model achieved the highest BLEU score (84.34), outperforming NLLB (79.25) by approximately 5 points, demonstrating superior translation quality for European language pairs. However, the EuroLLM Base model performed poorly (27.58), highlighting the critical importance of instruction tuning for translation tasks. In terms of inference speed, EuroLLM 1.7B Instruct demonstrated the fastest average translation time (0.529 s), marginally faster than NLLB (0.596 s), while the base model was significantly slower at 1.509 s per translation. Purpose-built sequence-to-sequence models (NLLB) showed strong performance, while causal LM models averaged 61.37 BLEU across all variants. The EuroLLM models require more memory (~3.5 GB vs. ~2.5 GB for NLLB's distilled version), with longer initial loading times for the instruction-tuned variant. The results present a compelling case for considering EuroLLM 1.7B Instruct as an alternative to NLLB in the translation pipeline, particularly given its specialised focus on European languages that aligns with the proposed platform's target markets.

Discussion

The results demonstrate that the proposed platform successfully integrates multiple AI-driven services into a cohesive XR learning environment that addresses both the communication needs of hearing users and the accessibility requirements of deaf users. The modular, service-oriented architecture enables independent scaling and updating of individual components, which is critical for maintaining system performance as user demands grow and AI models evolve.

The successful integration of six AI services, speech-to-text, text-to-text translation, text-to-speech, sentiment analysis, session summarisation, and IS translation, within a unified XR environment validates the premise that combining multiple AI modalities within immersive settings can create meaningful, accessible learning experiences. The IS-focused approach, leveraging International Sign Language as a lingua franca rather than a single national sign language, has the potential to broaden accessibility beyond national sign language boundaries and serve deaf learners from diverse linguistic backgrounds.

The avatar-mediated sign language delivery, while achieving animation latency under 300 milliseconds, represents an initial proof of concept that would benefit from further refinement. In particular, the quality of non-manual markers (facial expressions, head movements, body posture) is recognised in the broader literature as essential for comprehensible and natural signing,^{16,19} and their integration into the avatar system represents an important area for future development.

The benchmarking analyses provide quantitative evidence for technology selection decisions. The TTS evaluation confirmed that AWS Polly offers the best balance of latency, cost, and consistency for real-time VR applications, while the NLLB vs. EuroLLM comparison revealed that instruction-tuned causal language models can outperform purpose-built translation models in both quality and speed for European language pairs. This finding has implications not only for the proposed platform but also for the broader UTTER project's development of European language models.

Several limitations should be acknowledged. The IS dataset of 750 gesture videos, while sufficient for an initial proof-of-concept, represents a limited vocabulary that constrains the expressiveness of the translation system. Additionally, formal

usability studies with standardised instruments (e.g., System Usability Scale, NASA-TLX for cognitive load) have not yet been conducted and represent an important direction for future validation. The system has not yet been evaluated with end users wearing VR headsets in naturalistic learning scenarios, which is necessary to assess immersion, spatial presence, and actual learning outcomes.

The ethical dimensions of the platform were addressed through adherence to GDPR regulations, anonymisation of voice and gesture data, secure API access controls, and the application of FAIR data principles. Efforts were made to ensure fairness across languages and cultural contexts, particularly in the design and training of sign language avatars, to avoid misrepresentation and bias.

The platform presented in this study addresses a key gap identified in the literature: the absence of integrated, multimodal AI systems within XR that serve both deaf and hearing learners simultaneously. While previous work has typically focused on individual AI capabilities in isolation, such as speech recognition for captioning²³ or sign language recognition for classification,^{16,46} our system demonstrates the feasibility of orchestrating multiple AI services into a unified educational experience. This approach aligns with the vision articulated by Hirzle et al.,²¹ who identified the convergence of XR and AI as a high-potential research frontier, and extends it by grounding the integration in a concrete, deployable platform validated through comprehensive technical benchmarking.

From a policy perspective, the platform's focus on IS as a lingua franca for deaf communication across national boundaries aligns with the objectives of the European Accessibility Act and the EU's commitment to digital inclusion. By providing an XR-based learning environment that supports both spoken multilingual interaction and sign language translation, the proposed platform contributes to the broader agenda of equitable access to education, as articulated in the EU Digital Education Action Plan (2021–2027). The modular, cloud-native architecture ensures that the platform can be adapted to diverse institutional contexts, from formal language schools to informal community-based learning settings. Furthermore, the same underlying AI services have demonstrated applicability beyond language education, including accessible communication in professional and business meeting contexts.⁴⁷

Conclusions

This paper presented a comprehensive framework for integrating modular AI-driven services into immersive XR environments to support language learning for both deaf and hearing individuals. The platform combines speech-to-text transcription, multilingual translation, text-to-speech synthesis, sentiment analysis, and International Sign translation, all delivered through AI-powered 3D avatars within a Unity-based VR environment deployed on Meta Quest 3 headsets.

The system's modular architecture and successful integration of all AI components demonstrate the technical feasibility of the approach. Quantitative benchmarking of TTS services and multilingual translation models provided evidence-based justification for technology selection and identified promising alternatives for future integration.

Future work will focus on several priorities. First, the IS vocabulary will be significantly expanded by collecting and processing additional gesture videos from diverse interpreters, with improved gesture landmark normalisation to ensure smoother and more consistent avatar animations across signers. Second, avatar facial expressions and lip-sync functionality will be developed to provide the non-manual markers that are essential for natural sign language communication. Third, the single-user experience will be extended into a multiplayer VR setting where hearing and deaf users can communicate in real time, better showcasing the integrated sentiment analysis and translation capabilities and enabling collaborative language learning scenarios. Fourth, formal user studies with larger and more diverse participant groups will be designed and conducted, incorporating standardised usability instruments (e.g., System Usability Scale, NASA-TLX), pre/post learning assessments, and cognitive load measurements to produce quantitative evidence of learning effectiveness. Fifth, the EuroLLM 1.7B Instruct model will be further evaluated for integration into the production translation pipeline, with expanded benchmarking across additional European language pairs and domain-specific terminology. Sixth, the platform architecture will be extended to support additional XR hardware beyond Meta Quest 3, including standalone AR devices and desktop-based VR systems, to maximise accessibility across institutional contexts. Finally, the platform will be piloted in formal educational settings, including schools and language training centres, to assess real-world adoption, learning outcomes, and alignment with the EU Digital Education Action Plan's goals for inclusive, technology-enhanced learning.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this manuscript, the authors used generative AI-based tools, specifically large language models such as ChatGPT (OpenAI), solely to assist with language editing and consistency checks in limited sections. All

substantive decisions regarding the design of the review, screening, data extraction, analysis and interpretation were made by the authors. The authors carefully reviewed and edited all AI-assisted text and take full responsibility for the integrity and accuracy of the manuscript's content.

Open access software and AI models

All core AI models implementations central to the novelty and findings of this research utilise open-source libraries available under permissive licences for reuse:

- **Speech Recognition (OpenAI Whisper):** <https://github.com/openai/whisper> (MIT License)
- **Text to Text Translation (Meta AI NLLB):** <https://github.com/facebookresearch/fairseq/tree/nllb> (MIT License)
- **Pose Estimation (Google MediaPipe):** <https://github.com/google/mediapipe> (Apache License 2.0)
- **Sentiment Analysis:** Hugging Face Transformers— <https://huggingface.co/j-hartmann/emotion-english-distilroberta-base> (Apache License 2.0)
- **Summarization:** Hugging Face BART— <https://huggingface.co/philoschmid/bart-large-cnn-samsum> (MIT License)
- **Multilingual Translation Benchmarking (EuroLLM-1.7B Base):** <https://huggingface.co/utter-project/EuroLLM-1.7B> (Apache License 2.0)
- **Multilingual Translation Benchmarking (EuroLLM-1.7B-Instruct):** <https://huggingface.co/utter-project/EuroLLM-1.7B-Instruct> (Apache License 2.0)

These repositories contain the complete source code, model configurations, and training procedures necessary to replicate the AI integration methodology described in this paper.

Ethics and consent statement

This research did not involve direct experimentation with human participants. The International Sign (IS) gesture dataset used in this study was curated from publicly available, open-source video resources, specifically HandSpeak and SpreadTheSign, which are freely accessible online for research and academic purposes under permissive licences. No new video recordings of human signers were produced as part of this work. The gesture videos were processed computationally using Google MediaPipe to extract anonymised hand landmark coordinates; no personally identifiable information was retained in the resulting dataset. The AI models employed in the platform (Whisper, NLLB, RoBERTa, flan-t5-base-samsum) are publicly available open-source models used in their original or fine-tuned forms, and no additional training on personal data was conducted. The system architecture and all API services were designed with privacy-by-design principles, processing user inputs transiently without storing personally identifiable speech, text, or gesture data, in compliance with the European Union General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). No adverse events were reported during the development and testing of the platform. As no human participants were involved in any stage of this research, ethical approval and informed consent were not required.

Data availability

No data are associated with this article. This study did not generate or analyse datasets involving human participants. The platform's functionality was validated through technical benchmarking using publicly available AI models and synthetic test datasets as described in the Methods section.

Extended data

The IS gesture dataset developed for avatar animation is released as an open resource to support further research in sign language translation and accessibility technology development. The complete dataset and code necessary to replicate the IS animations are available in Zenodo: [10.5281/zenodo.18656296].⁴⁹ This dataset is released under a CC-BY 4.0 licence.

Data are available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International licence (CC-BY 4.0).

Acknowledgements

The authors gratefully acknowledge the UTTER consortium for the provision of the FSTP funding mechanism enabling the development of this research. The UTTER project partners, Maryam Hashemi (University of Amsterdam) and Amin Farajian (UNBABEL), are acknowledged for their guidance during the implementation of this study.

References

- Shliakhtina O, Kyselova T, Mudra S, et al.: **The effectiveness of the grammar translation method for learning English in higher education institutions.** *Eduweb.* 2023; **17**(3).
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Wu H, Su H, Yan M, et al.: **Perceptions of Grammar-Translation Method and Communicative Language Teaching Method Used in English Classrooms.** *J Engl Lang Teach Appl Linguist.* 2023; **5**(2).
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Divekar R, et al.: **Foreign language acquisition via artificial intelligence and extended reality: design and evaluation.** *Comput. Assist. Lang. Learn.* 2021; **35**(9): 2332–2360.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Tegoan N, Wibowo S, Grandhi S: **Application of the Extended Reality Technology for Teaching New Languages: A Systematic Review.** *Appl. Sci.* 2021; **11**(23): 11360.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Panagiotidis P: **Virtual Reality Applications and Language Learning.** *Int J Cross-Discip Subj Educ.* 2021; **12**: 4447–4454.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Godwin-Jones R: **Presence and agency in real and virtual spaces: The promise of extended reality for language learning.** *Lang. Learn. Technol.* 2023; **27**(3): 6–26.
[Publisher Full Text](#) | [Reference Source](#)
- Zhi Y, Wu L: **Extended reality in language learning: A cognitive affective model of immersive learning perspective.** *Front. Psychol.* 2023; **14**.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- ImmerseMe VR.
[Reference Source](#)
- MondlyAR.
[Reference Source](#)
- García C, Guzman A, Sánchez Ruano D: **Binding AI and XR in design education: challenges and opportunities with emerging technologies.** *Proceedings of the 26th International Conference on Engineering and Product Design Education (EPDE).* 2024; 247–251.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Hartholt A, Fast E, Reilly A, et al.: **Ubiquitous Virtual Humans: A Multi-platform Framework for Embodied AI Agents in XR.** *2019 IEEE International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Virtual Reality (AIVR).* 2019; 308–3084.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Zhang R, Zou D, Cheng G: **Concepts, affordances, and theoretical frameworks of mixed reality enhanced language learning.** *Interact. Learn. Environ.* 2023; **32**(7): 3624–3637.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Taborda CL, Nguyen H, Bourdot P: **Engagement and Attention in XR for Learning: Literature Review.** Reyes-Lecuona A, et al., editor. *Virtual Reality and Mixed Reality. EuroXR 2024. Lecture Notes in Computer Science.* Cham: Springer; 2025; **15445**.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Taborri J, Fournai P, Yeguas-Bolivar E, et al.: **The Use of Artificial Intelligence for Sign Language Recognition in Education: From a Literature Overview to the ISENSE Project.** *2023 IEEE International Conference on Metrology for eXtended Reality, Artificial Intelligence and Neural Engineering (MetroXR/AINe).* 2023; 122–126.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Strobel G, Schoormann T, Banh L, et al.: **Artificial Intelligence for Sign Language Translation – A Design Science Research Study.** *Commun. Assoc. Inf. Syst.* 2023; **53**.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Chaudhary L, Ananthanarayana T, Hoq E, et al.: **SignNet II: A Transformer-Based Two-Way Sign Language Translation Model.** *IEEE Trans. Pattern Anal. Mach. Intell.* 2022; **45**: 12896–12907.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Rodríguez-Correa PA, Valencia-Arias A, Patiño-Toro ON, et al.: **Benefits and development of assistive technologies for Deaf people's communication: A systematic review.** *Frontiers in Education.* 2023; **8**.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- European Union of the Deaf: **EUD Position Paper: International Sign Language.** 2018.
[Reference Source](#)
- Yin A, Zhong T, Tang LH, et al.: **Gloss Attention for Gloss-free Sign Language Translation.** *2023 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR).* 2023; 2551–2562.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Sylaiou S, Gkagka E, Fidas C, et al.: **Use of XR technologies for fostering visitors' experience and inclusion at industrial museums.** *Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference of the ACM Greek SIGCHI Chapter (CHI-GREECE '23).* 2023; **Article 21**: 1–5.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Hirzle T, Müller F, Draxler F, et al.: **When XR and AI Meet – A Scoping Review on Extended Reality and Artificial Intelligence.** *Proceedings of the 2023 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI '23).* 2023; **Article 730**: 1–45.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Tantaroudas ND, McCracken AJ, Karachalios I, et al.: **AI-Based Services to Support Language-Learning for Deaf and Hearing Individuals in Immersive XR Settings.** De Paolis LT, Arpaia P, Sacco M, editors. *Extended Reality. XR Salento 2025. Lecture Notes in Computer Science.* Cham: Springer; 2026; **15743**.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Radford A, Kim JW, Xu T, et al.: **Robust speech recognition via large-scale weak supervision.** *Proceedings of the 40th International Conference on Machine Learning (ICML 2023).* PMLR 202. 2023; 28492–28518.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- NLLB Team, et al.: **No Language Left Behind: Scaling Human-Centered Machine Translation.** *arXiv preprint arXiv:2207.04672.* 2022.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Liu Y, Zhu J, Zhang J, et al.: **Bridging the Modality Gap for Speech-to-Text Translation.** *arXiv preprint arXiv:2010.14920.* 2020.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Anwar MS, Shi B, Goswami V, et al.: **MuAVic: A Multilingual Audio-Visual Corpus for Robust Speech Recognition and Robust Speech-to-Text Translation.** *arXiv preprint arXiv:2303.00628.* 2023.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Camgöz NC, Koller O, Hadfield S, et al.: **Sign Language Transformers: Joint End-to-End Sign Language Recognition and Translation.** *2020 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR).* 2020; 10020–10030.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Zhou B, Chen Z, Clapés A, et al.: **Gloss-free Sign Language Translation: Improving from Visual-Language Pretraining.** *2023 IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV).* 2023; 20814–20824.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Zheng J, Wang Y, Tan C, et al.: **CVT-SLR: Contrastive Visual-Textual Transformation for Sign Language Recognition with Variational Alignment.** *2023 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR).* 2023; 23141–23150.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Wu X, Luo X, Song Z, et al.: **Ultra-Robust and Sensitive Flexible Strain Sensor for Real-Time and Wearable Sign Language Translation.** *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 2023; **33**.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Lugaresi C, Tang J, Nash H, et al.: **MediaPipe: A Framework for Building Perception Pipelines.** *arXiv preprint arXiv:1906.08172.* 2019.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Subramanian B, Olimov B, Naik SM, et al.: **An integrated mediapipe-optimized GRU model for Indian sign language**

- recognition.** *Sci. Rep.* 2022; **12**: 11964.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
33. ASL Transformer.
[Reference Source](#)
 34. HandSpeak – International Sign Language.
[Reference Source](#)
 35. Ahmed T, Devanbu P: **Few-shot training LLMs for project-specific code-summarization.** *Proceedings of the 37th IEEE/ACM International Conference on Automated Software Engineering.* 2022.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
 36. Boros K, Oyamada M: **Towards Large Language Model Organization: A Case Study on Abstractive Summarization.** 2023 *IEEE International Conference on Big Data (BigData)*. Sorrento, Italy: 2023; 6109–6112.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
 37. Bozkir E, Özdel S, Lau KHC, et al.: **Embedding Large Language Models into Extended Reality: Opportunities and Challenges for Inclusion, Engagement, and Privacy.** *Proceedings of the 6th ACM Conference on Conversational User Interfaces (CUI '24).* 2024; **Article 38**: 1–7.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
 38. Ramprasad S, Ferracane E, Lipton Z: **Analyzing LLM Behavior in Dialogue Summarization: Unveiling Circumstantial Hallucination Trends.** *Proceedings of the 62nd Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (ACL 2024).* 2024; 12549–12561.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
 39. Barbieri F, Camacho-Collados J, Espinosa-Anke L, et al.: **TweetEval: Unified Benchmark and Comparative Evaluation for Tweet Classification.** *Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics: EMNLP 2020.* 2020; 1644–1650.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
 40. Coqui TTS: **High-quality text-to-speech synthesis for researchers and developers.**
[Reference Source](#)
 41. Rhasspy contributors: **Piper: A fast, local neural text to speech system.** 2023.
[Reference Source](#)
 42. Picovoice: **TTS Latency Benchmark.** 2024.
[Reference Source](#)
 43. Schmid P: **flan-t5-base-samsum. Hugging Face model repository.** 2022.
[Reference Source](#)
 44. Bradski G, Kaehler A: *Learning OpenCV: Computer Vision with the OpenCV Library.* Sebastopol, CA: O'Reilly Media; 2008.
 45. SpreadTheSign.
[Reference Source](#)
 46. Srivastava S, Singh S, Pooja, et al.: **Continuous Sign Language Recognition System Using Deep Learning with MediaPipe Holistic.** *Wirel. Pers. Commun.* 2024; **137**: 1455–1468.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
 47. Tantaroudas ND, McCracken AJ, Karachalios I, et al.: **Enhancing Accessibility and Inclusivity in Business Meetings Through AI-Driven Extended Reality Solutions.** De Paolis LT, Arpaia P, Sacco M, editors. *Extended Reality. XR Salento 2025. Lecture Notes in Computer Science.* Cham: Springer; 2026; **15743**.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
 48. Tantaroudas ND, McCracken AJ, Karachalios I, et al.: **Transforming Career Development Through Immersive and Data-Driven Solutions.** De Paolis LT, Arpaia P, Sacco M, editors. *Extended Reality. XR Salento 2025. Lecture Notes in Computer Science.* Cham: Springer; 2026; **15742**.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
 49. Tantaroudas ND, McCracken AJ, Karachalios I, et al.: **International Sign Language Extractions and Data AVATAR animations.** *Zenodo.* 2025.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Open Peer Review

Current Peer Review Status:

Version 1

Reviewer Report 28 April 2026

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.25118.r71511>

© 2026 Faria D. This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Diego Resende Faria

Computer Science, Loughborough University Department of Computer Science (Ringgold ID: 152591), Loughborough, England, UK

This paper presents a technically well-engineered and timely contribution at the intersection of **XR, multimodal AI, and accessibility**. The integration of speech, translation, sentiment, and sign language into a unified immersive environment is novel and relevant, particularly in the context of inclusive education.

However, the work currently remains **primarily an engineering prototype with limited scientific validation**. The absence of user studies, limited statistical rigor, and insufficient evaluation of the sign language component significantly weaken the paper from a research perspective.

The manuscript would benefit from a clearer positioning as a **system demonstration and technical feasibility study**, unless additional experimental validation is provided.

Strengths

- Strong multimodal integration (rare in XR literature)
- Clear system architecture and implementation
- Relevant accessibility contribution (IS focus)
- Good engineering validation (latency, scalability)
- Alignment with EU policy and societal impact

Weaknesses

- Lack of user-centered evaluation
- Weak statistical validation
- Limited dataset size and benchmarking rigor
- Missing technical details for reproducibility
- Overstated claims about learning effectiveness

Specific Suggestions for Improvement

Must Address (Critical)

1. Add quantitative evaluation of IS translation model
2. Expand benchmarking datasets (translation, TTS)
3. Include statistical analysis with proper metrics
4. Clarify reproducibility:
 - Model architectures
 - Training details
5. Reframe conclusions to match evidence

Recommended

1. Conduct user studies (even small-scale pilot)
2. Add end-to-end system evaluation
3. Include comparison with baseline systems
4. Improve discussion on:
 - Limitations of IS dataset (750 samples is very small)
 - Generalization issues

improvements:

- Provide:
 - Full ML training pipeline (architecture, loss, optimizer, epochs)
 - Dataset split (train/val/test)
 - Evaluation metrics for IS translation
- Expand benchmarking dataset significantly
- Provide end-to-end latency analysis

The paper has **strong potential**, but requires **substantial improvement in scientific validation, statistical rigor, and reproducibility** to meet the standards expected for Open Research Europe.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Partly

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Partly

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Partly

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Partly

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Partly

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Human-Robot Interaction, Health AI, Child-Machine Interaction, Neuro-Affective Intelligence, Bayesian Machine Learning, Cognitive Robotics, Emotion AI, Affective Computing, Human Activity Recognition.

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to state that I do not consider it to be of an acceptable scientific standard, for reasons outlined above.
